

Start of a life health risk, struggles and coping as experienced teenage mothers

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ABSTRACT

Motherhood plays a vital role in society. It greatly influences the personality and disposition of a child. Teenage pregnancy is one of the major international social issues; nonetheless, the available literature seemed to address this issue quite indecorously. Thus, this study intended to identify the dynamics and causes of teenage pregnancy based on the context of those who experienced it. This study mainly focused on the personal health risk experiences, struggles, and coping of teenage pregnancy. A semi-structured in-depth interview with 35 teenage mothers was conducted. The researchers carefully transcribed the conversations, then read and re-read, then summarized the musings and verbalizations of the participants. A descriptive Phenomenological approach was utilized to analyze the data. Then, the missing psyche, unwanted, social judgment, embrace (MUSE) Phase of Teenage Pregnancy emerged. This was validated using "critical-friend and correspondence technique". Each phase reflects the onset, coping and struggles on becoming a teenage mother from conception to rearing the child. The discussion poses a unique perspective on understanding the phases of teenage pregnancy coming from the point of view of those who experienced it, which is vital in making efforts to prevention and intervention.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Mothers greatly influence the personality and disposition of the child who will become a member of society. It can be considered as the noblest occupation since it requires selflessness, instincts, tremendous patience, and willingness to sacrifice most things in life to rightfully raise their children. It plays a vital role in the society since mother's upbringing can greatly influence the future generations' thought processes and disposition [1], [2]. Such an important role requires utmost maturity to predict success.

Teenage pregnancy is constantly a major social problem in both developed and underdeveloped countries. Annually, over 16 million adolescent females give birth worldwide [3]. Girls from 15-19 years of age are facing an unplanned pregnancy and the consequences that come along with it at an early stage of development. At this age level, the physical and emotional readiness of the girls is insufficient to motherhood responsibilities. This phenomenon is a social problem that affects the welfare of the girls and their families as well as the society as a whole.

The United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) has defined adolescent pregnancy as a pregnant girl, usually between the ages of 13-19 [2], [4]. The world health organization [5] reported that in developing countries like the Philippines, approximately 16 million girls ranging from age 15 to 19 years and millions under the age of sixteen give birth each year. Alarming, among the association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) States, the Philippines have one of the highest teenage birth rates (2013). Moreover, the leading cause of mortality for 15 to 19-year-old girls across the globe was complications during pregnancy and childbirth. According to the young adult fertility and sexuality study (YAFS) performed by the University of the Philippines population institute (UPPI) and the demographic research development foundation (DRFF) in 2013, one out of every ten Filipina teens aged 15 to 19 years old was already a mother [6], [7]. Furthermore, around 2.6% of Filipina teens in the same age range are already pregnant with their first kid, while 13.6% have begun childbearing. United nations populations fund (UNFPA) [6] on the other hand, reinforced the feeling of urgency expressed by national economic development authority (NEDA) [7] and populations commission (POPCOM) in 2019, describing the country's alarmingly rising adolescent pregnancy rate as a national emergency.

Childbearing in adolescence increases the risk of poor health outcomes for both mother and child, and the younger the adolescence, the greater the risk [8]. Pregnancy during adolescence is linked to an increased risk of health issues such as anemia, sexually transmitted diseases (STIs), pregnancy complications, and psychological distress consequences like depression and even suicide. Adolescents who become pregnant at a young age face additional risks, such as having a greater age gap with their partners, which puts them at a higher risk of domestic violence as well as human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) and other sexually transmitted disease (STIs) [8].

Teenage pregnancy can be considered an international crisis since it directly and indirectly, result to different health risk issues and social problems. As young girls undergo teenage pregnancy, their physical health and development as well as their education, emotions, social life, and the society's future, are all impacted. Its weight has an impact on family life, exposing them to physical issues and financial insecurity [9], [10]. Researchers linked teenage pregnancy to various social problems. In 2015, research by Undiyaundeve showed that poor parenting, poverty, dating, violence, age difference in relationships, environmental factors for children, medical factors, are the main causes that contribute to the effects of teenage pregnancy [10], [11]. In addition, teenage pregnancy is a social problem since children born to teenage mothers are more likely than children to older mothers to suffer health, social and emotional problems [1]. Many of the adverse social issues associated with adolescent motherhood include being more likely than their peers to live in poverty, being unemployed, or having minimal wages and low educational achievement [1]. In addition, children of adolescent mothers are more likely to become adolescent parents themselves due to their mothers' lack of guidance and moral authority [9].

Some of the ramifications of adolescent pregnancy [10]. For starters, teen births are linked to a lower mother's yearly income [10]. Eighty percent of adolescent mothers want assistance at some time in their lives. Second, adolescent mothers are more likely to drop out. Only about a third of adolescent mothers were graduated from high school. Finally, young births are linked to higher rates of alcohol and drug misuse, worse educational attainment, and decreased earning potential among teen dads [10], [12]. Moreover, according to UNICEF, there are adverse repercussions for the child and siblings of teenage parents, such as: i) the child of a teen mother is more likely to live in poverty; ii) grow up without a father; iii) become a victim of neglect or abuse; iv) do poorly in school; v) become involved in criminal activities; vi) abuse drugs and alcohol; vii) and eventually become a teenage parent and perpetuate the cycle the younger sibling of a teen mother is more likely to accept sexual initiation teenage years accept sexual initiation [2], [4].

If a conception is unplanned, the woman may not be able to get the prenatal care she and her baby require, or she may not be healthy enough to take the child to term. Adolescents are typically unprepared for the reality of having a child, as Paunan explains, and complicated relationships, financial load, social shame, and parenting may all be stressful, putting a newborn in danger [12]. For adolescent moms, young people, and pregnant teens, it must involve education, skill-building, clinical, and social support.

As aforementioned, teenage pregnancy is continually being a major social problem leading to health risks and social problems. However, the available literature seemed to address this issue quite indecorously. Teenage pregnancy is a pressing social concern whether in developed or developing countries are often viewed as problems that needed proper solutions [13]. Given the number of aspects which can be associated with teenage motherhood and plethora of studies in different disciplines done across its vital causes, the underlying factors rest to be vague and elusive. Generally, there is a focus on various correlates, but details as to why particular antecedent conditions should lead to early age at first birth are not imminent.

Therefore, this qualitative study attempted to capture and understand the crux of teenage pregnancy based on the first-hand information from those who experienced it. This study will focus on the possible reasons, struggles, and coping mechanisms before, during, and after pregnancy. Specifically, this study aimed

to answer the central question “how physical health risks, struggles and coping were is experienced and understood by people who have undergone teenage pregnancy?” This will identify the dynamics and causes of teenage pregnancy in rural communities in the Philippines where teenage pregnancy is continuously raising. This creates a portrait of the system and cycles affecting the aforementioned never-ending social issue.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

Qualitative phenomenology was used to capture the essence of facing struggles and coping as a phenomenon. Phenomenology is regarded as "the science of the essence of consciousness focused on defining the idea of intentionality and the meaning of the lived experience from the first person's point of view" [14], [15]. The location of this study was in selected rural areas in Cagayan Valley, Philippines where the data on teenage pregnancy has been consistently rising. According to the survey, the Cagayan valley region has the second-highest adolescent pregnancy prevalence in the country, which is on the increase this year [16].

The researcher purposively recruited 35 teenage mothers who experienced teenage pregnancy. The following are some of the eligibility requirements for selection: i) mothers who experienced teenage pregnancy for three years and above; ii) twenty-five years old and below; and iii) able to follow oral and written directions. Participants were excluded from the research if they had: i) communication and understanding issues and ii) were above the age of 25.

The researcher used a two-part instrument to surface the process of onset, facing struggles, and coping among teenage mothers. The first part is shown in Table 1, which is the participants' robofoto, a Dutch term defined as “a cartographic sketch of the subject” [14], [17]. This is gathered to establish the baseline characteristics of the teenage mothers under study. The second part is the in-depth conversation intended to elicit the participants' own experience which regards their path to living before, during, and after giving birth to a child. The in-depth interview/conversation is guided by key conversation queries from the aid memoir.

Table 1. Profile of the participants

Profile	(n=35)	(%)
Age		
18-21	11	31.43
21-25	24	68.57
Onset of pregnancy		
10-14 years old	4	11.43
15-19 years old	31	88.57
Length of being a teenage parent		
1-3 years	6	17.14
4-6 years	19	54.29
7-9 years	9	25.71
10 years and above	1	2.86
Mother's occupation		
Teaching	1	2.86
Farmer	9	25.71
Others	5	14.29
Father's occupation		
Overseas Filipina Worker (OFW)	7	20.00
Farmer	23	65.74
Others	5	14.29

Captivating the crux of the phenomenon, an in-depth conversation with the participants and their selected significant other was conducted. Before the data collection procedure, the participants were asked to sign an informed consent and were given a full, explanation of the purpose and design of the paper. On the permission of the participants to be included in the study, individual in-depth interviews with the participants based on their time of availability. Interview locations were also chosen by the participants themselves, with the assumption that they will be more honest and comfortable in a familiar environment [14], [17]. It also aims to establish the best rapport and to create an emotionally stimulating environment between the participants and the researchers. A semi-structured interview was enforced to create a free-flowing conversation without alterations in the focus and direction of the interview. Along with the main questions, follow-up queries were raised to be able to explore the participants' responses [14], [17]. Interview questions were open-ended and the flow of discussion was determined by the participants, though in some instances, the researcher needed to

clarify and probe deeper on certain responses thru follow-up questions. The researcher asked permission of the participants for the conversations to be taped to facilitate transcription and data analysis. The audio-recorded interviews were manually transcribed by the researcher. The in-depth, semi-structured interview was conducted using the Filipino language. Each interview lasted about 40 to 90 minutes.

Vital information from the pen-portrait (robotfoto) was reviewed, tallied, and analyzed. Transcription of the live experiences gathered from the in-depth interview was manually encoded and completed into texts. Transcribed experiences have undergone thorough reading and re-reading. Then, it was documented via cool and warm analyses [14], [17]. The researcher employed a repertory grid to uncover an eidetic primary meaning of the event, which helped with the cold and warm analyses of the obtained material. The procedure of Paul Colaizzi was used to get to the heart of the problem (online gaming disorder) under investigation [18]. Themes and categories were discovered, and the material was winnowed into digestible information in order to uncover distinct phases and hierarchies, eventually tying the texts into theoretical [14], [15], [17], [18]. Moreover, the chosen expressions and verbalizations of the participants were carefully translated to the English language to facilitate the understanding of non-Filipina readers. The themes that emerged were characterized as truthfully and as accurately as possible. Critical friend technique and correspondence techniques were done to guarantee the trustworthiness and truthfulness of the gathered data [15], [18].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of the qualitative inquiry comprehensively presented the phases of the experiences of students who undergone teenage pregnancy as they experienced physical, psychological, sociological, and spiritual difficulties. The following themes emerged from the richness and thickness of the field texts. Figure 1 shows the themes and subthemes that were emerged and extracted. The superordinate themes are the general and encompassing factors that yielded various subthemes. As seen from the results are mixed and diverse data about the conflated experiences of the participants' facing struggles and coping in different contexts. A comprehensive and detailed report on each subtheme is discussed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. MUSE phases of teenage pregnancy

This study illustrated four phases that teenage mothers had to go through from the beginning to the end. Each phase illustrated their pains and struggles and how they manage to cope with those problems. Teenage mothers have gone through tremendous negative effects on the physical, mental, social, and spiritual facets of life. Most importantly, this body of work found that the role of parental support and guidance is crucial in preventing teenage pregnancy.

3.1. Missing psyche enjoying the youth

Table 2 shows that without the presence of guidance and parental care, teenage girls explore things on their own with people of their age. Hence, with the adventurous nature of adolescence, things happened hastily leading to regrettable situations. Additionally, material things to cover for the emotional presence of a parent resulted in the adolescents' further explorations to attain their emotional needs. The attention-seeking behavior leads to a search for a youthful quest to find oneself, which in turn, leads to unpleasant events that they enjoyed.

Moreover, the influence of social media and peers had impacted their young search for pleasure, emotional bond, and physical explorations. The aggressive nature of the adolescence stage of life is channeled by whatever they found on the Internet specifically the misguided use of social media-inspired wild imaginations and sexual explorations. Enjoying their youth, adolescent girls enter into uneducated sexual activities that led them to the unwanted situation of being pregnant at a very young age. Interestingly, this happened in rural areas where families are viewed to be conservative. Thus, the influence of social media and different online platforms with unregulated sexual content plays a vital role in their imprudent sexual activities. As the verbalizations of the participants revealed:

Table 2. Missing psyche enjoying the youth

Subthemes	Excerpts
Absence of parental and proper guidance	"I grew up with both my parents are busy with their work, I only see my mother every two or three years for less than two months and my father is always busy at the farm or busy with his circle of friends." R11 "I live with my grandparents; both my parents are Overseas Filipino Worker (OFWs) I only see them once in a while. Though I am with my grandparents, I can't say that they guide me since they give me what I want, just letting me be." R28
Adolescence's curiosity explorations and attention-seeking behavior	"I never planned to be pregnant at a young age but I don't know, I think curiosity killed my dreams..." R1 "When I was younger, escaping from our home or in school to meet a college boy and to explore my body with him gave me that sense of fulfillment." R6 "During that time, I just really want to know what it feels like to be hugged, to be kissed... to feel loved... without really thinking about the consequences of my action." R30
Sexuality and sexual health of teenagers	"That time, I thought, all of my friends were doing it with their boyfriends, why shouldn't I...? so I did it... and it was satisfying, I enjoyed it too much that the fear of being pregnant hadn't stopped me... it was...it happened." R16 "I was trying to explore on the pleasure and gave in to sexual desires." R21 "Nobody taught me about sex, it not often of a topic...I just gave in to sexual desires without knowing the consequences." R32

The alarming fact that the teenagers entered into a risky sexual behaviour represents the degree of teenage pregnancy amongst sexually active teens [19], [20] even in rural areas of the Philippines. Uneducated sexual behaviors especially among young people can lead to severe threats of sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) or human immunodeficiency virus (HIVs) [21], [22]. This worrying fact suggests that there is a minimum progress in reducing teenage pregnancy despite that it was emphasized in millennium development goals (MGD) together with a high mortality rate among teenage mothers [20], [23].

Experiencing teenage pregnancy seemed to originate from a lack of guidance and parental concern with developing adolescents. The study findings indicated that one of the imminent reasons for teenage pregnancy was lack of parental attention. With the innate urge of adolescents' curiosity, explorations and attention-seeking behavior played a vital role in entering uneducated sexual interactions which led to early and unwanted pregnancy. Gselamu and his colleagues argued that teenage pregnancy is more common in young girls who grew up in a permissive environment [24]. Parental relationships with adolescents play a vital role in preventing such ordeals [25]. Thus, it is suggested that parents or caregivers should nurture open conversation in their homes, particularly about sex, sexuality, and dating, to teach youngsters, particularly females, how to take care of themselves in such situations [13], [26].

Furthermore, peer influence and unregulated social media also took part in the poor judgment of young women. Further, the undeveloped rationality of one adolescent paired with another can lead to juvenile adventures which might result in an unexpected phenomenon [27], [28]. In 2019, the world health organization (WHO) stressed that adolescents should be encouraged to be educated about the societal impact of their overwhelming impulses [5]. Hence, proper guidance and attention both of parents and the community is crucial in preventing the adolescents to hastily performing actions that might lead to regrettable decisions in life. Teenage pregnancy is more frequent among children of single parents, as is exposure to most sexual content on television, sexuality in the media, and pornographic and sex chatrooms frequented by adolescents who are particularly tuned to engage in sexual behaviors [24].

3.2. Unwanted physical and psychological health risk

As seen in Table 3, changes in their physiological, psychological, sociological, and spiritual began after the conception. Pregnant teenagers started to feel the physical discomforts of pregnancy when physical changes from childhood to adolescent period had just commenced. Adjusting to physical changes during pregnancy was tougher since they had just begun to enjoy their growing youthful body. They also mentioned health difficulties such as bleeding during pregnancy, tremendous headaches, vomiting, sleepless nights, infections, and neumerous physical health risks during and after pregnancy.

Table 3. Unwanted physical and psychological health risks

Subthemes	Excerpts
Health risk and physical discomfort	<p>"I had difficulty breathing, Doctors said my BP was high, I even experienced the pre-eclampsia. I was confused, it was physically difficult."</p> <p>"I will never forget the changes that happened in my body and the pain I have to go through during my early pregnancy. I was just starting to undergo physical changes from childhood then I have gone thru so much physical change as my tummy began to grow due to pregnancy." R19</p> <p>"Back then, when I am starting to have morning sickness, it was shocking, it is uncomfortable. I cannot eat properly; I can't have fun the way I used to." R27</p>
Physical and mental adjustments	<p>"At the start, I was in denial, I don't know what to do, it was my worst nightmare came true, I don't know protected sex back then, I was too naïve and I almost killed myself...If only I thought of things like this first." R5</p> <p>"I was in and out of the hospital, I cannot understand what they are saying but I had an infection, one day they said I am anemic. It was hard. I could not sleep or eat properly...It felt like I am about to die." R13</p>
Psychological struggles (anxiety, overthinking, and disorientation)	<p>"I just wanted to become another person, I almost killed myself or the baby inside me at least, I know it is bad but that is how I felt before." R1</p> <p>"At first, I almost opted for abortion. I was so lost, confused and wanted to die." R16</p> <p>"I was so afraid; I don't know what to do. I just wanted to disappear." R27</p> <p>"To cope with the stress of my teenage pregnancy, I used to go to church and asked for forgiveness...for guidance and blessing." R34</p>

Along with the discomforts and adjustments from the physical changes are psychological struggles. Generally, the participants expressed their utmost confusion and dilemma as to what they were going thru. Due to extreme anxiousness, some of them even opted to attempted abortion which led them to depressive symptoms such as helplessness, loneliness, and even thought of taking their own lives.

Interestingly, this was the time that the participants found their way to real friendship and solidarity with their families. Generally, they stated that these were the times when they felt the love and concern of their parents even when they were upset. In those tough times, most of them found their way to spiritual growth. It played a strong impact on their acceptance of the phenomenon and felt closer to God. As excerpted by the verbalizations of the participants.

Physiological, emotional, sociological, and spiritual changes brought the thrills and pains of the unprecedented life-changing event. Along with physical discomforts and pain experienced by the teenagers were anxiety and confusion which often led to depressive symptoms. Early pregnancy among adolescents can lead to physiological and psychological struggles that weaken the mind and body [29], [30].

This phenomenon is attributed to adverse consequences among adolescent mothers, their children and the community [31], [32]. Some pregnancy complications may occur more frequently in teenagers than in women of right age [5]. Furthermore, there is a socio-economic disadvantage among teenage mothers [21], [33]. Among the complications are hypertensive disorders at a very young age, anemia, malnutrition, human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infections and other sexually transmitted diseases and iodine deficiency [5], [34], [35]. Being pregnant at a very young age can also hinder their physical growth and development [5], [35].

Teenage mothers are also more likely to have a low birth weight, grow up poor, live in a single parent household, and experienced abuse and neglect, while children born as a result of teenage pregnancy are more likely to have a low birth weight, grow up poor, live in a single-parent household, and experienced abuse and neglect [19], [36]. Furthermore, the daughters of adolescent mothers are more likely to become adolescent moms, whereas sons are more likely to be imprisoned [37], [38]. This phenomenon can result in depression and an increased probability of mortality of the offspring as well as the young mother [13]. Also, the world health organization (WHO) stated that during pregnancy, teenage mothers have a higher risk of miscarriage which can lead to psychological distress [5]. Gsemalu and his colleagues claimed that "the stress associated with pregnancy, sense of rejection by friends of relatives, lowered depression and emotional trauma, fear of future and deprivation usually challenges faced by teenage mothers which may expose to mental illness" [39]. Interestingly, protective factors such as peer support and spiritual grasps helped teenage mothers cope with stress and confusion. This supported the findings of Dippel *et al.* that the traumatic results that the teenager experiences during pregnancy can be lessened with the emotional support of people who

care for them and the spiritual grasps that came along with it [37], [39]. The school environment and peers who can understand the teenage mother protect them from developing a mental illness and other unpleasant happenings during pregnancy [32], [35].

3.3. Societal judgement struggles of inherently unforgiving societal norms

On the other hand, Table 4 shows the musings of participants' hardships when it comes to dealing with the standards of society. Participants felt that stoutly sense of guilt especially for the broken dreams and hopes of their parents. Additionally, the expectations and respect not only of the society around them but also of themselves were greatly damaged.

Table 4. Societal judgement struggles of inherently unforgiving societal norms

Subthemes	Excerpts
Challenges of broken hope, promises, and expectations	"Drama started when I finally told my parents about it, it was full of disappointment, tears, and broken dreams. It was the time when shame sunk in." R12 "I felt like it was the end of everything, I have broken all the promises and expectations of my parents. I mean I am a Valedictorian, an honor student. I was so done." R34
Prejudice and stereotypes of violating the societal norm	"Gossips, social judgment, all the labels they can use to describe me was the worst. It had broken my confidence; I think that was the reason my life was always ruined." R7 "The hardest part was not telling my parents, it was letting our neighbors and relatives know. I couldn't go outside I could not. Bear their looks and hurtful remarks." R23
The societal impact of child-rearing of a child	"I was so clueless, was even afraid to touch my baby...but I learned to get by with the help of my family but I had a hard time dealing with my neighbors." R5. "I faced financial difficulties, it was different back then, I am so ashamed to have my parents buy everything so I worked first. I was lucky my parents sent me back to school." R1 "I was just trying to figure life, and then I had to raise a child because of a major mistake. And the society around me was not helping. I am judged with every bit of my move." R32

According to them, the hardest part was when the community around them saw them as something to be ashamed of. Gossips as to how dishonorable they were, the judgmental look in their eyes, and the snide remarks of the society broke their self-esteem and tarnished their sense of self-worth. They refused to go outside for a long period because of the humiliation and embarrassment they felt. Furthermore, the societal impact of rearing their child and their development as a teenager greatly affected their sense of confidence, belongingness, and dignity as a person. They experienced a total decline in social connections, limited activities to know themselves further and some have to stop their studies for a while to take care of their child.

Furthermore, most participants faced financial difficulties as they have to work whatever job is available to feed their child. In some cases, the child's father opted to work but that wasn't enough to feed the family. Meanwhile, after giving birth most of the participants were sent back to go school to continue studying. This helped them cope with the struggles they faced. To them, this phase was the toughest part.

Surprisingly, the most challenging part of teenage pregnancy was not the pregnancy itself but coping with the society around them. Breaking the expectations, crushed dreams, and aspirations and the thought everything from that point was uncertain. The societal judgments and the fundamentally unforgiving social standards are especially in rural areas. Deviating from a social norm especially in rural areas in most Asian countries tends to be unforgivable [19], [20], [37]. The distress of teenage pregnancy was deeply rooted in the shame and guilt that society will make you feel [24], [26]. Gsemalu and his colleague argued that aside from the physical struggles, rejection, and avoidance from the people who used to have a close relationship with the teenagers can lead to depressive symptoms [24]. Furthermore, being unprepared for parenthood, sudden monetary burden realization that the teen will have a lifelong connection with the other parent or ending the relationship with the other parent, disruption in their life plans, and increases the teenagers' stress level [14], [21], [37].

Pregnancy might well be a life-changing experience for a teenage girl at any age, lowering educational attainment and socioeconomic status, as well as stress, dislike, malice, boredom, and discontent in her family setting [19], [39]. Single-parent children are more prone to adolescent pregnancy and adolescent exposure to the majority of sexual content on television, media sexuality, and pornographic and sex chat rooms, and are predominantly inclined to engage in sexual behaviors [22], [24]. As a result, adolescent pregnancy is a huge global psychological and economic difficulty that affects both developed and developing cultures. More empirical research is needed since it has an impact on teens' social-psychological well-being, as well as academic disruption, dropout rates, and public perception.

3.4. Embrace the start of a new life

Table 5 illustrates the last phase where the participants revealed that as time passed, they started to have realizations that they need to be survive for their child. For them, it was like burying the degradation of the past and starts a new life. Facing struggles and difficulties broke the old selves and created a new one to survive the storm that came their way. According to them, having a baby at a very young age was like a second chance to walk away from their old habits and start anew. The process was extremely difficult and self-destructive; it was life-changing both in positive and negative ways. As excerpted from the verbalizations of the participants:

Table 5. Embrace the start of a new life

Subthemes	Excerpts
Facing struggles and coping with it	"Having a baby at a very young age, "hard" was an understatement. It was hard-hitting but I learn to cope with it, I made it my inspiration. I have to; he gave me a new meaning." R6 "The process was rough, it was life-changing in good and bad ways but I have learned to go on with it, be strong and cope with it by raising my child and pursuing my dream with the help of my family." R28
Embracing motherhood and everything that goes with it	"When it is there you'll have to get by and that happened to me...it was tough but i have to change and learned not to care with anything but my child." R15 "I came to realize that life was not mine on my own, I need to care for my child more...life outside my world is the same... but I think I have changed I had to accept motherhood and everything in it. The financial burden, the pains in my body and the judgmental society." R22
Adjusting to everything new	"Everything was new, and it was a tough road to take. And I would recommend it to any girl trying to figure life out. But when it happened, it was not the end of everything we can always start anew." R10 "The whole thing is different, yes it was rough and I was not a good example when it happened to someone, my only advice is to never give up...never listen to gossips and be on your world." R14

The start of a new life is both a challenge and an opportunity. In the case of teenage mothers in rural areas is starting a new means of dealing with huge self-image, self-respect, societal expectations, and financial struggles. "The effect of teenage pregnancy could be devastating since it is not only on the teenage-mother, it also continues with their education and social life" [24]. The socio-economic problems started to arise at the beginning of a child's birth and became one of the major problems of teenage parents [33]. Furthermore, the adolescent mother may be exposed to greater dangers, which include cognitive, linguistic, and socio-emotional delays, as well as challenges that endure after delivery and issues with cognition, language communication, and interpersonal skills [38], [39]. It also reveals their regret and sadness, as well as the emotional anguish they had throughout the pregnancy and even after delivery, as well as psychiatric issues. Rejection by male contemporaries, relatives, and classmates is another painful event that reduces connection. Pregnancy, at any age, may be a life-changing experience that affects a teenage girl's scholastic achievement, financial level, stress, dislike, malice, boredom, and dissatisfaction in her family environment.

Embracing motherhood and making their child as the life inspiration served as their ultimate coping mechanism. As expressed by them, being a teenage mother crushed their future along with the goals, dreams, and plans their selves and family had. It had sacrificed their growth and enjoyment that people of their age used to enjoy. However, it gave them a new sense of direction, a path where they have to take to raise their respective successfully. They were full of regrets; they tended to blame their parents and other people around them. But they have to pick up themselves, forced to cope with all the hardships that come along with being a very young mother. It narrowed down their option to conquer the world and be the best that they can be to become at least a good mother to their child along with the hardships they are continuously facing with it.

Teen pregnancy is a global psychological and economic issue that affects both developed and developing cultures. Its impacts require further empirical research because it affects teens' physical and social-psychological well-being, as well as their holistic development and public image. Parental involvement, school direction, and guided sexual education were all important factors in averting the problem.

4. CONCLUSION

Teenage pregnancy affects the holistic development of the adolescent mother and the community around her. It is one of the main social problems that need proper and inclusive intervention programs to be addressed. As to this study, the main factor on the onset of teenage pregnancy was due to a lack of guidance, protection, and proper care of parents, the school, and the community. Parental guidance among the developing and adventurous nature of adolescents is vital in preventing teenage pregnancy.

Physical health risks involving not only teenage pregnancy but imprudent sexual activities as well should be one of the concerns of intervention programs to be conducted in rural communities. Proper education of the youth, both girls and boys about sex and sexuality and its dynamics can be crucial in preventing teenage pregnancy. Teenage pregnancy, especially in rural areas, leads to stigma and poor self-image among teenage mothers. The societal judgment and financial problems were lifelong struggles among teenage mothers. Nevertheless, raising their child, trying to be a good mother is their main coping mechanism. Starting a new life with new goals, new aspirations and new inspiration to move forward requires grit, determination, and motherly love to move forward.

Education with regards to sexual activities and their impact on oneself in the community needed to be formulated to prevent such social problems. The results of this study can be a pattern to formulate an intervention for teenage pregnancy prevention. Delicate topics such as sexual education, prejudice, and social media need to be discussed broadly among teenagers. Likewise, parents needed to be educated on the impact of their care and attention on their children.

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